

CREATE A NEW DESIGN PROJECT OF THE BASE DRAWING OF THE SUN SKIRT

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ABSTRACT. This article presents the results of experimental research on the dimensions and additions to the construction drawing of skirts from waisted clothes by the figure of girls recommended. The obtained results are recommended based on the analysis of tables and charts based on the calculation book.

Keywords: *base grid, size, wheel, circle, radius, radius, half circle, full circle, third part.*

A skirt is a garment that covers the lower part of the body. Skirts can be one-piece or unbuttoned, cropped, or uncut. Skirts are the main waist clothes of girls. In ensembles, the shape of the skirt is subordinate to the general composition of the suit. [1]

The variety of skirts is mainly created due to the use of the different arrangements of some elements and structural lines in the construction of internal structures. At the same time, the shape of the skirt depends on the structure of the figure of the gymnasts and the characteristics of the fabrics intended for the development of skirts.

A variety of skirts can be obtained through two structural straight and conical bases. The classic form of a skirt is a straight skirt. The two sides of the

back and front pieces and pleats along the waistline are the basis of existing skirts. The number of pleats in the waist and their location depending on the shape of the bust.[2]

Based on a straight skirt, there are different patterns (front and back pieces are symmetrically located in the middle, evenly along the circumference of the hips), and different amounts of pieces (four, six, eight, etc.) construction of skirts are processed.

To show the breasts expressively, the silhouette of straight skirts is designed to fit well in the hips, and the longitudinal cuts are made in the form of a complex curve and flared down like a gode.

Cone skirts are characterized by somewhat flared hems and no frills at the waistline. The upper part of the skirt and the shape of the skirt will depend on its shape and the structure of the figure of athletic girls.

Analysis of experimental results. To build a drawing of a girl's skirt, it is necessary to know the size of the girl and its construction value.

The following dimensions will be needed to construct a drawing of a rhythmic gymnastics skirt.

As shown in the picture

1. The length of the skirt
- 2 waist length
- 3 waist circumference
- 4 Circle number

Table 3

The necessary dimensions for the construction of the drawing of the skirt.

Determination of dimensions	Dimension name	Size value
S_t	waist circumference	27

S_b	Top semicircle	34
D_s	Back waist length	32
D_{iz}	Skirt length	40
Supplements to be given		
P_t	Extra waist circumference	1
P_b	Additional hip circumference	2

The base mesh of the skirt consists of three horizontal and five vertical stripes. Horizontal lines waist, bust, hem lines. Vertical lines are the middle of the back lobe, the side, the middle of the front lobe, the lines of the back lobe and the front lobe. (Fig. 3.2).

Figure 2. Construction drawing of a straight skirt base

To construct the drawing grid, a right angle is constructed at the T point: the horizontal line defines the waistline, and the vertical line defines the midline of the back. TB and TN incisions are placed on the bottom, which defines the bust and hemlines.

$$TB=0,5*D_{ts}=0,5*32=16$$

$$TN=40$$

From points T and N, horizontal lines are transferred to the left. The width of the skirt on the bust line or the middle line of the front part is determined by the TT_1 section.

$$BB_1 = S_b + P_b = 34.0+2.0=36$$

The sideline marks point SS_2

$$BB_2=0.5(S_b + P_b)-1.0=0.5(34.0+2.0)-1.0=17$$

The arc of the front and rear wheels is determined using sections B_1B_4 and BB_3 .

$$B_1B_4=0.4*B_1B_2 = 7.6$$

$$BB_3=0.4* B_1B_2=0.4*17=6.8$$

A vertical line rises from points B_3 , B_2 , B_4 , and B_1 up to the intersection of points Bl_3 , Bl_2 , Bl_4 , and Bl_1 with the waistline. 1 cm above the Bl_2 point, the Bl_2' point is marked (Fig. 2). Points T, T', T_2' , T_4' , and T_1 are connected by a straight line.

The sum of the rolls on the waistline is worked out according to the following formula.

$$\sum B=(S_b + P_b):2-(S_t:2)=(34+2):2-(27:2)=36:2=18-13,3=4,5$$

Here:

$\sum$ The total value of the V-wheel

S_b - hip semicircle

P_b – Extra thigh semicircle

S_t - waist semicircle

2^{nd} constant value

According to the result, we calculate the back, front, and side screws using the following formula.

$$\text{Rear wheel width } 0.25\sum V=0.25*4.5=1.125$$

Front-wheel width $0.3\sum V=0.3*4.5=1.35$

Side scroll width $0.45\sum V=0.45*4.5=2.025$

To build the sides of the waistline, the width of the back, front, and side waistlines is divided equally in half from the points T_3' , T_2' and T_4' to the left and right sides in a row.

Length of rods:

The length of the back screw is 10-12 cm

The length of the front part is 6-8 cm

The width of the side scroll is 12-14 cm

In rhythmic gymnastics clothes, waist loops are closed (Fig. 3).

Figure 3.3. Close the skirt pleats

A drawing of the base of the skirt is required in the case of conical expansion. To construct the drawing of the conical skirt, two radii from the center O are defined. The radius of the upper arc is R_t , the radius of the lower arc is R_p .

$$R_t = K(S_t + P_b)$$

Figure 3. The structure of the conical skirt.

Scheme 4 is a cone-shaped skirt

The radius of a full-circle skirt is calculated using the following recommended equation 1

For full-circle (sun-shaped) skirts, if the skirt pattern is a full circle and is calculated by putting it in the formula (Fig. 1,2,3), the results are explained based on the following drawing.

$$\text{Waist circumference} = 2 \times p \times \text{radius}$$

Waist circumference is 27 sizes

$$r = \frac{St}{2\pi} = \frac{27}{2 \times 3,142} = 4,455$$

Here:

r= radius

p=3.142

Waist circumference is 27 centimeters

Constructive drawings of rhythmic gymnastics skirt

CONCLUSION

In the proposed article, the calculation of full circle, half circle, one-third circle skirt, and quarter circle skirt was developed. Based on the proposed model, certain dimensions were taken into the construction drawing, and construction drawings were made by selecting structural additions.

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